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Abstract

While a rapid development of renewable energy sources and deployment of wind farms are necessary to reach climate goals, there are concerns about negative impacts of wind farms on ecosystems. In previous studies, these effects were analysed on small spatial scales, however, since ecological processes occur at broader scales, impacts should be assessed at European, national and sub-national scales.

This deliverable is the second version (D1.8 (b)) of WIMBY's impact assessment on terrestrial and marine fauna. High-resolution, spatially explicit impact models and analyses for target species are provided for selected pilot regions: Styria (Austria) and Pantelleria (Italy). A workflow for a fine-scale assessment of potential effects of targeted wind power plants on wildlife is demonstrated for the pilot region Rogaland (Norway) and can be found in D1.7 (a).

Ecological niche models for selected target species showed that habitats suitable for species can overlap, thereby, careful siting of wind farms and the protection of areas of high sensitivity can minimize impacts of wind farms on these species. Additional mitigation measures, for example painting of turbine blades and towers, curtailment or deterrents can reduce risks of collision.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AUC	Area Under the Curve
AVM	Additive Value Model
CR	Critically Endangered
DD	Data Deficient
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
EN	Endangered
ENM	Ecological Niche Models
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
LC	Least Concern
OWF	Offshore Wind Farm
NT	Near Threatened
RE	Regionally Extinct
SDM	Species Distribution Model
TSS	True Skilled Statistic
VIF	Variance Inflation Factor
VU	Vulnerable

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

While a rapid development of renewable energy sources and deployment of wind farms are necessary to reach climate goals, there are concerns about negative impacts of wind farms on ecosystems. The effects of wind farms on wildlife are usually assessed at small spatial scales, but ecological processes occur at broader scales. Thus, impacts should be assessed at European, national and sub-national scales. The objective of this Deliverable 1.8 (b) is to assess the impact of wind farms on terrestrial and marine fauna. High-resolution, spatially explicit ecological niche models and analyses for target species are provided for selected pilot regions: Styria (Austria) and Pantelleria (Italy). The document is organised in 5 Sections. Section 1 provides an introduction into the state of the art of the effects of wind farm on ecosystems and wildlife and the importance of assessing the impact of wind farms on terrestrial and marine fauna on a broader geographical scale. Section 2 focusses on high-resolution ecological niche models and connectivity models for a selection of threatened wildlife species in the onshore pilot region Styria (Austria). Within Section 3, ecological niche models are implemented at a small-scale combining occurrence and environmental data for the offshore pilot site at Pantelleria Island (Italy). Section 4 refers to D1.7 (a), which provides a full environmental impact assessment following Norwegian standards and contributes to preliminary results and data from the Norwegian marine Energy Test Centre's AI powered, bird monitoring system to enrich the understanding of the potential impacts on the local marine environment from different offshore wind power plant types. In Section 5, the main outcomes are summarised and mitigation measures are highlighted.

The summed habitat suitability and averaged habitat connectivity maps for Styria predict high habitat suitability and connectivity in some regions of the pilot site Styria, which reflect the species-specific habitat requirements of the analysed species. The produced maps can be used by stakeholders and help to raise awareness and visualize potential habitats suitable for these threatened species when wind farm deployment is planned in specific regions in Styria. The combination of habitat suitability maps for the Pantelleria pilot study showed a potential sensitive area extending along a

northwest-southeast axis in the southern part of Pantelleria. The sensitivity map can be used to identify key marine areas for different species, with the aim of supporting offshore wind farm siting. The environmental impact assessment for the Rogaland pilot study showed that the potential impact of the additional turbines at the pilot site could have a medium to large negative impact on biodiversity (see D1.7 (a)). However, mitigation measures such as painting one rotor blade black, automatic shutdown during times of high bird activity and timing the installation of infrastructure is expected to significantly reduce these potential negative impacts. The preliminary results from the AI powered bird monitoring indicate the prevalence of certain bird species, flight direction and height, but need to be assessed in more detail once data over longer time periods become available.

1. INTRODUCTION

Renewable energy is considered essential for mitigating climate change and achieving energy security (REN21 2023). In this regard, the International Energy Agency (IEA) outlines the need for increasing wind energy to 390 GW by 2030 as one of the strategies to meet the net zero climate targets of 2050 (International Energy Agency 2021). Part of the European Union's REPowerEU plan includes investment in renewables such as wind energy to meet its energy security targets (REN21 2023). The expansion of wind energy capacity is of concern because wind farms can have unintended negative ecological impacts through habitat modification and collisions (Northrup and Wittemyer 2013; Schöll and Nopp-Mayr 2021).

Construction of wind farms and related infrastructure results in habitat modification – loss, degradation, or fragmentation (Jones et al. 2015; Watson et al. 2024) which in turn can negatively impact species abundance (Fernández-Bellon et al. 2019) and habitat use (Abramic et al. 2022; Ellis et al. 2022). The operation of wind farms can impact species behaviour and activity (Coppes et al. 2020a; Thomsen et al. 2006; Tolvanen et al. 2023). Some species have been observed to avoid wind farms because of shadow flickering by the turbine blades (Taubmann et al. 2021) and noise generated by the turbine rotors (Taubmann et al. 2021), while other species have altered their flight path to avoid wind farms (Therkildsen et al. 2021; Villegas-Patraca et al. 2014). Collision with wind turbines is well documented in several volant species and results in mortality in bats (O'Shea et al. 2016) and birds (Serratosa et al. 2024) which can have cascading impacts on the population of a species (Schippers et al. 2020). However, there are cases where wind farms can positively impact species abundance (Galparsoro et al. 2022; Werner et al. 2024) and habitat use (Janßen et al. 2015; Łopucki et al. 2017) and in some cases they might not have any impact (de Lucas et al. 2005; McNew et al. 2014).

The negative ecological impacts of wind farms can be mitigated or altogether prevented by avoiding development in biodiversity sensitive areas (Arnett and May 2016). Generic guidelines exist that regulate the development of wind farms around key biodiversity areas such as national parks and wilderness areas (e.g., Bennun et al. 2021). However, an issue with this is that biodiverse areas also exist outside of protected areas such as

national parks. Thus, it is important to identify such areas particularly for species that are of high conservation concerns, assumed to form metapopulation systems and/or have been shown to react sensitively to disturbance. Such information can then be used by stakeholders and considered in the early planning and site selection stage of a potential wind farm development (Bennun et al. 2021).

2. PILOT REGION: STYRIA

2.1 Background

While onshore wind farms were often deployed in open areas (e.g., agricultural areas) in Central and Southern Europe during the last decades, construction of wind farms in forested areas is more common in Northern European countries, which are heavily forested (Enevoldsen 2018). With the ongoing efforts to increase renewable energy production in Central Europe, there is the need to expand the search for potential wind farm locations towards additional sites located in forested areas or at higher elevations, which offer good wind resource potential (European Environment Agency 2009). In Germany, the development of wind farms in forested areas has increased in recent years and around 2000 wind farms are already located in forests, with 90% of these wind farms having been built in the last 10 years (FA Wind 2021). Potential wind farm sites in forested or high altitudinal areas are usually located in rural and undeveloped areas (Diffendorfer and Compton 2014). Construction of wind farms in remote areas is thereby often accompanied by deforestation to expand the road network or establish additional transmission lines (Enevoldsen 2018), potentially affecting wildlife species occurring in the respective areas (Diffendorfer et al. 2019).

Construction of wind farms includes the development of different infrastructures such as turbine pads, roads, and transmission lines which are spatially highly scattered and cause high amount of habitat fragmentation (Jones et al. 2015). This can limit species movement and in turn result in isolated populations (Pruett et al. 2009). Construction can also lead to loss of nesting habitat and in turn impact species population (Zimmerling et al. 2013). Even if suitable habitat is available some species avoid areas around the turbines (Tolvanen et al. 2023). Thus, it is important to identify which areas contain suitable habitat for a species to reduce loss of such areas.

Correlative Ecological Niche Models (ENMs) have become increasingly used to support conservation decisions (Zurell et al. 2022) and to assess species risk in relation to renewable energy infrastructures (e.g., Smeraldo et al. 2020). ENMs correlate species presence with environmental variables to predict species habitat spatially and temporally (Elith and Leathwick 2009). These models use species presence data which are readily available from public data repositories and are logistically easier to implement compared

to other spatial models that use GPS data from tagged individuals (e.g., Marques et al. 2020).

Habitat connectivity is of major importance for the long-term persistence of species and populations, especially in the context of patchy distributions of populations within human-dominated landscapes (Allendorf et al. 2012). Connectivity hereby describes the permeability of the landscape to facilitate movement of individuals. As such, connectivity depends on the species attributes and landscape characteristics. In the past decades, expert-based habitat assessments have been used and reclassified into resistance surfaces which have then been used to analyse connectivity. Nowadays, correlative ENM are preferred. The underlying concept assumes the habitat quality to be directly associated with resistance to connectivity, i.e., areas with low habitat quality present higher resistance to movement than areas with good habitat quality. While this assumption certainly cannot be made for all species (e.g., for many species, habitat suitable for breeding differs from habitat suitable for movement), some indicator species are particularly sensitive to changes in habitat quality, which in turn drives their dispersal patterns. As such, resistance surfaces from species distribution models (SDMs) have already proven useful for predicting the landscape's permeability for indicator species such as the Western capercaillie (*Tetrao urogallus*, Milanesi et al. 2017) and the Black grouse (*Lyrurus tetrix*, Kunz et al. 2021).

Habitat connectivity can be assessed using circuit theory (McRae et al. 2008). In circuit theory, the landscape consists of a network of nodes connected by edges. The nodes can represent habitat patches or populations while edges can represent resistance to movement from patch to patch. When a voltage is applied between two nodes, current flow depends on the voltage applied and the resistance offered by the edges (McRae et al. 2008). By making use of circuit theory and describing movement by using voltage, quasi-random walk is simulated inferring no a priori knowledge of the individual about the landscape. The output of the analysis results in normalized current which is equal to the raw current divided by flow potential. Flow potential is current flow in null conditions i.e., the resistance of the all the pixels/cells is 1 (Landau et al. 2021). Ultimately, current can be considered as a proxy for species movement with higher

current indicating higher potential for movement or in other words the habitat promotes connectivity.

The aim of the study is to inform local communities and raise awareness of potential ecological impacts of onshore wind farm locations on habitat suitability and connectivity of multiple species in Styria, Austria. The study has two objectives. Firstly, to model ecological niche by correlating species presence from Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, GBIF 2024) with different environmental variables using an ensemble of machine learning algorithms and producing habitat suitability maps. Secondly, to model habitat connectivity by using the produced habitat suitability maps and circuit theory (McRae et al. 2008) via the Omniscape Julia package (Landau et al. 2021) to produce habitat connectivity maps. In this second version of the impact assessment on terrestrial fauna in Styria, Austria (D1.8 b) we present high-resolution, spatially explicit impact models and associated outputs for 23 species (10 amphibian species, 1 bat species, 8 bird species, and 4 butterfly species). The selection of the species is based on four criteria – habitat, migration, conservation status, and data availability. Forest and woodland-dwelling species were considered because new wind turbine development in Styria is expected to be deployed along mountain ridges covered by forest and woodland, as these areas in higher altitudes coincide with areas of high wind potential (Amt der Steiermärkischen Landesregierung, 2019). Only non-migratory species were selected because these species stay within their habitats throughout the whole year. Thus, potential effects of wind farms on the species can be considered to occur throughout the species' yearly life cycle, while there is no need to account for additional effects that could arise during migration or in overwintering habitats, which often cannot be assessed adequately. The species were also limited to those threatened (near threatened, vulnerable, endangered, or critically endangered) at the national level (Austria) and/or regional level (Styria) in the respective Red Lists (amphibians: Gollmann 2007, ÖKOTEAM 2021; bats: Spitzenberger 2005; ÖKOTEAM 2021; birds: Dvorak et al. 2017, Albegger et al. 2015; butterflies: Höttinger and Pennerstorfer 2005, ÖKOTEAM 2021). Species had to have at least 100 presence points, assumed to be adequate, for robust modelling (see section 2.1.2).

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Study area

The Austrian province of Styria covers an area of approximately 16.400 km², situated at the easternmost border of the Alps (Figure 2.1). As such, Styria is mostly covered by mountainous areas, ranging from 200 m above sea level (a.s.l.) to 3000 m a.s.l. The study area is mostly covered by coniferous forests (>60%, Land Steiermark 2024), with settlements in the valleys and rock and glaciers on high mountains. The south-eastern part, however, ranges into lowlands, with the largest city (Graz) being situated in a pre-alpine basin.

A set objective of Austria's federal government is to cover 100% of the total national electricity consumption from renewable energy sources by 2030 (Bundeskanzleramt Österreich 2020). Aside from enhancing energy efficiency and accounting for increasing demand, the production of renewable energy needs to increase (Federal Ministry for Sustainability and Tourism and Federal Ministry for Transport Innovation and Technology 2018). Electricity production through wind power grossed about 7.2 TWh annually in 2021. In order to reach Austria's set goal of 100% electricity covered by renewable energy, wind power production presumably needs to increase by another ~ 10 TWh annually. Thereby, wind power potential can be found especially in the eastern parts of Austria, with the federal state of Styria accounting for 13% of Austria's potential capacity (Austrian Energy Agency 2023).

Here, habitat suitability and connectivity were modelled across Styria. However, for three amphibian species – *Bufo viridis*, *Rana dalmatina*, and *Salamandra atra* – the study area was limited to their IUCN distribution ranges within Styria because it was unlikely that these species occur outside their ranges.

Study area

Figure 2.1 Location of study area, showing Styria, Austria.

2.2.2 Species occurrence data

Species occurrence (hereafter: presence) records were downloaded from GBIF (GBIF 2024). Presence records were limited to i) those from the year 2000 onwards and ii) classified as 'human observation'. GBIF contain some records that are erroneous and this needed to be accounted for prior to analysis. Duplicate records based on latitude and longitude were removed. Depending on the species, records from urban land cover such as "industrial or commercial units", "road and rail networks and associated land", "port areas", "airports", "mineral extraction sites", "dump sites", "construction sites", and "continuous urban fabric" were removed as these were likely to be dubious records. To reduce spatial autocorrelation and sampling bias, records less than 250 m (i.e., the spatial resolution of the predictor variables) from one another were removed randomly using the spThin R package (Aiello-Lammens et al. 2015). In total, data for 23 species (10 amphibian species, 1 bat species, 8 bird species, and 4 butterfly species) were included in the analysis as they had a minimum of 100 presence points after data cleaning and thinning (Table 2.1).

Amphibians

The yellow-bellied toad (*Bombina variegata*) is a small amphibian favoring shallow, sunlit, and temporary waterbodies like puddles, ditches, and slow-moving streams (Barandun et al. 1997, Barandun and Reyer 1997, Kwet 2022, Scheele et al. 2014). The species is distributed across central and southeastern Europe (Kwet 2022, Ogradowczyk et al. 2024). Populations in Austria are primarily found in lower elevations, including Styria, where it inhabits agricultural landscapes and forest clearings (ÖKOTEAM 2021). In Europe, the species is listed as least concern on the IUCN Red List with a declining population trend (Ogradowczyk et al. 2024, Table 2.1). But due to habitat loss and fragmentation, the yellow-bellied toad classifies as vulnerable in Austria and Styria, highlighting regional population declines from agricultural intensification, pollution, and land-use changes (ÖKOTEAM 2021, Ogradowczyk et al. 2024, Scheele et al. 2014).

The common toad (*Bufo bufo*) is widely distributed across Europe (Cogălniceanu et al. 2024). It prefers a variety of habitats such as forests, meadows, and gardens, but primarily relies on still or slow-moving water bodies like ponds and small lakes for breeding (Cogălniceanu 2024, Kwet 2022). Apart from this, the species is terrestrial for most of the year (Crnobrnja-Isailović et al. 2012, Kwet 2022). While the common toad is listed as least concern on the IUCN Red List due to its broad range and adaptability, local declines in species abundance might occur due to habitat loss, road mortality, and water pollution (Cogălniceanu 2024). In Austria and Styria, it classifies as near threatened, primarily due to road kills (Gollmann 2007, ÖKOTEAM 2021, Table 2.1).

The European green toad (*Bufo viridis*) is distributed across eastern Europe, extending into parts of southern Europe and Russia. It is present throughout Austria, including Styria, although populations can be patchy (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2023a). This species is highly adaptable, inhabiting diverse environments such as forests, forest steppes, scrubland, grasslands and alpine areas, but also inhabiting urban areas (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2023a, Kwet 2022, Landler et al. 2023). For breeding, green toads require temporary or permanent water bodies like ponds, ditches, or puddles (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2023a, Kwet 2022). Despite its adaptability, the species is vulnerable to habitat fragmentation, pollution, and agricultural intensification, leading to localized declines. The green toad is listed as least concern on the IUCN Red List (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2023a), but in Austria, it is classified as

vulnerable (Gollmann 2007), while in Styria, it is critically endangered due to habitat destruction and urbanization (ÖKOTEAM 2021, Table 2.1).

The European tree frog (*Hyla arborea*) is considered an endemic species to Europe with declining population trends, primarily distributed in central Europe and extending to parts of southern Europe (Agasyan et al. 2024). In Austria including Styria, its distribution is fragmented, with populations concentrated in areas that provide suitable breeding habitats like temporary ponds and wetlands with abundant aquatic vegetation, usually not exceeding altitudes of 800 m asl (Kwet 2022, ÖKOTEAM 2021). It inhabits warm, terrestrial, flower-, shrub- or forest-rich habitats near breeding sites such as ponds and ditches (Agasyan et al. 2024, Kwet 2022, ÖKOTEAM 2021). While still classified as least concern by the IUCN Red List (Agasyan et al. 2024), the species is considered vulnerable in Austria in Styria mainly due to habitat loss and fragmentation (Gollmann 2007, ÖKOTEAM 2021, Table 2.1).

The alpine newt (*Ichthyosaura alpestris*) and the smooth newt (*Lissotriton vulgaris*) are semiaquatic salamander species, which are globally listed as least concern, but while the European smooth newt populations are stable (Poboljšaj et al. 2024), the populations of the alpine newt are declining (Denoel et al. 2024). In Austria and on a regional level (Styria) the two species are listed as near threatened (Gollmann 2007, ÖKOTEAM 2021, Table 2.1). Both species are widely distributed in Europe and can be found at most altitudes, ranging from lowlands up to high elevations (*I. alpestris* and *L. vulgaris* up to 2500 and 2000 m asl, respectively, Kwet 2022). For larval development, both species need still or slow-moving shallow aquatic patches (Denoel et al. 2024, Kwet 2022, Poboljšaj et al. 2024).

With the ongoing decline of suitable habitat in Europe, the agile frog (*Rana dalmatina*) population trend is decreasing, and while the species is still listed as least concern in the IUCN Red List (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2023b), the agile frog is listed in the Red List Austria (Gollmann 2007) and the Red List Styria (ÖKOTEAM 2021) as near threatened and vulnerable, respectively (Table 2.1). The species is widely distributed in central and southeastern Europe and occupies lowlands and wetlands within forest and adjacent meadows but can also be found up to an elevation of 1700 m asl in the Alps (Kaya et al. 2023, Kwet 2022).

The common frog (*Rana temporaria*) is widespread in Europe (except for Spain, Portugal, IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2022, Kwet 2022). The species is listed as least concern with a stable population in the IUCN Red List Europe (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2022), and as near

threatened in the Red List of Austria (Gollmann 2007) and Styria (ÖKOTEAM 2021, Table 2.1). The common frog can be found along the altitudinal gradient ranging from lowlands up to 3000 m asl in the Pyrenean mountains, and inhabits open landscapes (gardens, wetlands) and woodlands (Kwet 2022). The alpine salamander (*Salamandra atra*) can be found in alpine meadows and woodlands (Kwet 2022, Martel et al. 2023). The common fire salamander (*Salamandra salamandra*) is widely distributed in western, central and south Europe (Kwet 2022, Martel et al. 2023). *S. salamandra* occupies habitats in broad-leaved forests but is also dependent on heterogeneous and shallow streams or ponds for breeding (Kwet 2022, Manenti et al. 2009). The distribution of both species partly overlaps in the European Alps, indicating interspecific niche overlap in suitable habitats (Werner et al. 2017). *S. atra* is listed as least concern (Martel et al. 2024) and *S. salamandra* is listed as vulnerable in the IUCN Red List (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2023c, Table 2.1). Both species are listed as near threatened in Austria (Gollmann 2007) and Styria (ÖKOTEAM 2021).

Bat

The lesser horseshoe bat (*Rhinolophus hipposideros*) is a geographically widespread species found from Africa to Eurasia which has experienced population declines across north-central Europe (Dool et al. 2013). Although it is listed as least concern at the European level (Russo and Cistrone 2023) it classifies as vulnerable in Austria (Spitzenberger 2005), and as near threatened in Styria (ÖKOTEAM 2021, Table 2.1). The species is predominantly found in forest-rich, near-natural regions connected by linear structures, with a preference for deciduous and mixed forests (Bontadina et al. 2002, Dietz et al. 2016, Dietz and Kiefer 2020, Reiter 2004). Usually favoring warm lowlands or south-facing valley slopes, the lesser horseshoe bat increasingly inhabits higher altitudes, including alpine areas due to agricultural intensification (Dietz et al. 2016, Dietz and Kiefer 2020).

Birds

The stock dove (*Columba oenas*) is widely distributed throughout Europe and prefers open habitats with shrubs and trees, such as woodland-edge habitats (BirdLife International 2021a). Habitat use highly overlaps with other members of the *Columbidae* family (Floigl et al. 2022). The species uses a broad variety of breeding sites, such as holes excavated by Black Woodpeckers (*Drycopus martius*) as a secondary hole nester, but also

breeds in rabbit burrows, buildings or in dense vegetation (BirdLife International 2021a, Kosiński et al. 2011). While the stock dove is classified as least concern at the European (BirdLife International 2021a) and national scale (Dvorak et al. 2017), the populations in Styria are near threatened (Albegger et al. 2015, Table 2.1).

The Syrian woodpecker (*Dendrocopos syriacus*) occupies open woodlands with high availability of dead wood and can be found in small forest patches close to heterogeneous agricultural landscapes (f.e. orchards) (Albegger et al. 2015, Michalczyk and Michalczyk 2023) but can also breed in sparsely wooded areas in urban landscapes (Figarski and Kajtoch 2018, Fröhlich et al. 2022). In contrast, middle spotted woodpeckers (*Dendrocoptes medius*) – as a forest specialist (Fröhlich et al. 2022) – are often occupying territories in large forest patches with old tree stands (Michalczyk and Michalczyk 2023). In Austria, *D. medius* can mainly be found in old deciduous oak forests (Albegger et al. 2015). Riparian woodlands are often occupied by lesser spotted woodpeckers (*Dryobates minor*) (Chiatante et al. 2019) and grey-faced woodpeckers (*Picus canus*) (Albegger et al. 2015). Both species (*D. minor*, *P. canus*) can also nest in orchards or parks (Albegger et al. 2015). The four woodpecker species are considered as least concern in Europe (BirdLife International 2021a, Table 2.1), which also applies for *D. medius* and *D. minor* in Austria, but *D. syriacus* and *P. canus* classify as near threatened in Austria (Dvorak et al. 2017). In Styria, *D. medius*, *D. minor* and *P. canus* are listed as near threatened on the Red List (Albegger et al. 2015). In the period 1968 – 2000, a small number of breeding pairs of *D. syriacus* was determined in Styria, but the species is considered regionally extinct today (Albegger et al. 2015).

The western capercaillie (*Tetrao urogallus*), the black grouse (*Lyrurus tetrix*) and the hazel grouse (*Tetrastes bonasia*) are three forest grouse species of conservation interest. While they are currently listed by the IUCN red list as least concern (BirdLife International 2021b,c, BirdLife International 2024), ongoing declining trends within central European populations shed a focus on these species (Jahren et al. 2016; Storch 2007b, Table 2.1). The western capercaillie and the black grouse are mainly ground dwelling, and rather sedentary with low dispersal abilities, hence habitat characteristics are considered key factors for the species occurrence, and the species are sensitive to changes in habitat (Geary et al. 2015, Picozzi et al. 1992, Storch 2000). As such, the western capercaillie acts as an umbrella species for Central European mixed forests rich in biodiversity (Pakkala et al. 2003; Suter

et al. 2002), whereas the black grouse is considered as an indicator species for tree-line ecotones with a patchy mixture of open areas and small groups of trees (Sachser et al. 2017; Storch 2007a). The hazel grouse is a ground-dwelling forest-specialist species occurring in both natural and extensively managed forest (Matysek et al. 2018). It is generally a sedentary species whose boreal populations tend to migrate (Matysek et al. 2018). Its population is decreasing in several European countries and is listed in Annex I of the European Council Directive (Birds Directive) on the protection of wild birds (79/409/EEC, Kortmann et al. 2018).

Butterflies

The large copper butterfly (*Lycaena dispar*) and the marbled white butterfly (*Melanargia galathea*) are listed as least concern at European level (Van Swaay et al. 2010) and in Austria (Höttinger and Pennerstorfer 2005). However, in the pilot region Styria, *L. dispar* is listed as endangered, and *M. galathea* is as vulnerable in the Styrian Red List (ÖKOTEAM 2021, Table 2.1). Both species are relatively broadly distributed throughout Europe. While *L. dispar* occupies broad-leaved deciduous forests, grasslands and wetlands, *M. galathea* can be found in mesophile grasslands, dry calcareous or siliceous grasslands and humid grasslands, but also in broad-leaved deciduous forests and mixed woodland (van Swaay et al. 2006).

The dryad butterfly (*Minois dryas*) is listed as least concern at the European level with decreasing population trends (van Swaay et al. 2010). However, it is near threatened in Austria (Höttinger and Pennerstorfer 2005), and vulnerable in the pilot region Styria (ÖKOTEAM 2021, Table 2.1). Its distribution mainly covers southern central Europe (van Swaay et al. 2010). The species occupies (dry calcareous, dry siliceous, humid and mesophile) grasslands but can also be found in broad-leaved deciduous forests (van Swaay et al. 2006). The availability of forest edges has a positive effect on immigration of females and functional connectivity (Akeboshi et al. 2015).

The clouded apollo butterfly (*Parnassius mnemosyne*) is scattered in central southern and in northern Europe, being increasingly abundant across the Caucasus and Middle east. It can be found in grasslands (e.g. alpine and subalpine, humid or mesophile), but also in broad-leaved deciduous forests and mixed woodland (van Swaay et al. 2006). The larvae of *P. mnemosyne* feed on the larval food plant *Corydalis cava*, which often occurs along forest edges and in the transition zones between grasslands and deciduous forests (Habel et al. 2022). While the clouded apollo butterfly

is listed at the European level (van Swaay et al. 2010) and in Austria (Höttinger and Pennerstorfer 2005) as near threatened with declining population trends, it is critically endangered in the pilot region Styria (ÖKOTEAM 2021, Table 2.1).

Table 2.1 List of study species along with their conservation status (Red List assessment) at European, national (Austria) and regional (Styria) level and the number of presence points downloaded from GBIF and used in the analyses (GBIF 2024). Red List Categories following IUCN Red List criteria: DD = Data Deficient, LC = Least Concern, NT = Near Threatened, VU = Vulnerable, EN = Endangered, CR = Critically Endangered, RE = Regionally Extinct.

Taxa	Species	Red List Category: Europe / Austria / Styria	Presence points
Amphibians	<i>Bombina variegata</i>	LC / VU / VU	472
	<i>Bufo bufo</i>	LC / NT / NT	1112
	<i>Bufo viridis</i>	LC / VU / CR	295
	<i>Hyla arborea</i>	LC / VU / VU	354
	<i>Ichthyosaura alpestris</i>	LC / NT / NT	629
	<i>Lissotriton vulgaris</i>	LC / NT / NT	590
	<i>Rana dalmatina</i>	LC / NT / VU	455
	<i>Rana temporaria</i>	LC / NT / NT	1133
	<i>Salamandra atra</i>	LC / NT / NT	383
	<i>Salamandra salamandra</i>	VU / NT / NT	930
Bat	<i>Rhinolophus hipposideros</i>	LC / VU / NT	112
Birds	<i>Columba oenas</i>	LC / LC / NT	363
	<i>Dendrocopos syriacus</i>	LC / NT / RE	235
	<i>Dendrocoptes medius</i>	LC / LC / NT	350
	<i>Dryobates minor</i>	LC / LC / NT	349
	<i>Lyrurus tetrix</i>	LC / NT / VU	382
	<i>Picus canus</i>	LC / NT / NT	494
	<i>Tetrastes bonasia</i>	LC / NT / DD	200
	<i>Tetrao urogallus</i>	LC / NT / VU	337
Butterflies	<i>Lycaena dispar</i>	LC / LC / EN	251
	<i>Minois dryas</i>	LC / NT / VU	290
	<i>Melanargia galathea</i>	LC / LC / VU	819
	<i>Parnassius mnemosyne</i>	NT / NT / CR	110

2.2.3 Background points

Since information on absence of species was not specifically recorded and available in the dataset downloaded from GBIF, but necessary to analyse data and build ENMs, we substituted absence data with background data, which characterize the environment in the pilot region Styria. Background points were generated using random stratified method. Thereby, background points were randomly generated and stratified across the

different land cover classes, so that all land cover classes were included. Background points were at least 250 m from each other and 1000 m from presence points. The number of background points was equal to the number of presence points.

2.2.4 Predictors

To model ecological niches, habitat, topographic, and climate predictors were included. Habitat included land cover and tree cover density (%) from the European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (European Environment Agency 2018a, b), tree height (m, Turubanova et al. 2023) as well as distance (m) to nearest waterbody derived from Umweltbundesamt GmbH (2024) and distance (m) to nearest forest, conifer forest, urban areas, and alpine grassland (grassland occurring ≥ 2000 m in elevation) derived from the land cover (European Environment Agency 2018a). Topographic predictors included a digital elevation model (DEM, m, European Space Agency 2023) as well as slope (degrees) and aspect (degrees) which were derived from the DEM using the terra R package (Hijmans 2023). Climate variables included average daily minimum temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), average daily maximum temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), average temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), average mean temperature in the warmest month ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), average mean temperature in the coldest month ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), average minimum temperature in the coldest month ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), average maximum temperature in the warmest month ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), average relative humidity (%), and average precipitation (mm) from BioClim Austria (Lehner et al. 2024).

The predictors – land cover (100 m), tree cover density (100 m), tree height (30 m), elevation (90 m) – were resampled (from their original spatial resolution) using the terra R package (Hijmans 2023) to match the spatial resolution of the climate predictors i.e., 250 m. The derived predictors – distance to nearest waterbody, forest, conifer forest, urban areas, and alpine grassland as well as slope and aspect had a spatial resolution of 250 m. The coordinate system used was MGI Austria Lambert/EPSSG:31287. The land cover predictor was reduced from the initial 32 classes to 8–10 classes depending on the species habitat preference. The reclassification of land cover classes was discussed with species-specific experts.

The numerical predictors (i.e., all predictors except for land cover) had different ranges and units which could be weighted differently and influence

model accuracy. To overcome this, they were scaled using the terra R package (Hijmans 2023) so that mean and standard deviation of each predictor was 0 and 1, respectively.

Instead of using all the aforementioned predictors for modelling the ecological niche of a species, a subset of predictors was selected depending on the species, based on previous findings where available and species general habitat requirements (Annex Table A7.1). Subsequently, highly correlated predictors (≥ 0.7) were removed by calculating the variance inflation factor (VIF) using the 'vifcor' function in usdm R package (Naimi et al. 2014; Annex Table A7.1). Here, 'vifcor' finds a pair of variables which has the maximum linear correlation (≥ 0.7) and excludes the one with a greater VIF. The process was repeated until no pair of variables with a high correlation coefficient (≥ 0.7) remained (Naimi et al. 2014).

2.2.5 Ecological Niche Models

The data was divided into training (70%) and testing (30%) datasets. The training dataset was used for model training and optimisation, while the testing dataset was used for accuracy assessment of both the habitat suitability and habitat connectivity models (see section 2.1.6).

Models were trained and optimised using the 70/30% training/testing cross-validation method with 50 repeats using the caret R package (Kuhn 2008). The models used included random forest, gradient boosting model, artificial neural network, k-nearest neighbour, support vector machine, and generalised linear model. The trained and optimised models were then used to predict habitat suitability. Habitat suitability ranged from 0.0 to 1.0 which indicated lowest and highest probability of suitability, respectively.

The accuracy and general fit of the models were assessed using the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve (Fielding and Bell 1997) and the True Skilled Statistic (TSS, Allouche et al. 2006). AUC measures the area underneath the entire ROC curve (sensitivity versus False Positive Rate). It ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates a perfect model and values less than 0.5 indicate a random model (Fielding and Bell 1997). TSS is equal to sensitivity plus specificity minus 1. It ranges from -1 to +1, where +1 indicates a perfect model and values less than 0 indicate a random model (Allouche et al. 2006). The models with the highest

accuracy were then selected to build an ensemble model (unweighted). The accuracy of the ensemble model was assessed using AUC and TSS as well as by regional experts for the specific species as recommended by Morales et al. (2017).

To visualise habitat suitability of the three species and their overlap with potential wind farm sites chosen by researchers and the general public in the WIMBY interactive map, the ENMs were converted from probabilistic values (0.0 to 1.0) to binary values (0/1 i.e., unsuitable/suitable). Therefore, maximum sensitivity-specificity sum maximisation approach (Liu et al. 2005) was used to select the optimal threshold.

All analyses for modelling ecological niche were carried using R (R Core Team 2023).

2.2.6 Habitat connectivity

The probabilistic Ecological Niche Models were used as the resistance layer i.e.,

$$\text{resistance} = 1 - \text{habitat suitability}$$

where high suitability represents low resistance and vice-versa. However, for amphibians, road network was included as an additional resistance i.e., pixels/cells that overlapped with a road was given the highest resistance value. The binary (suitable and unsuitable) Ecological Niche Models were then used as the current source layer.

To assess habitat connectivity, the two parameters radius and block size must be set beforehand in an initialisation file. The radius parameter represents the radius in pixels of the moving window used to identify sources to connect to each target (Landau et al. 2021). This parameter is likely to influence the output of the models, thus different values were considered – 25, 50, 75, and 100. Here, 100 was the maximum value as higher values resulted in an increase in computational cost and it is unlikely the species would move more than a radius of 100 pixels (each pixel is 250 m) or 25,000 m. The block size parameter is an odd integer that coarsens the source strength for identifying target pixels and assigning source strength values (Landau et al. 2021). This parameter had a negligible effect on the output (Landau et al. 2021) and was set to 5. When block size is 5 the source strength grid is broken up into chunks of 25 pixels (5x5 blocks) with only the centres

of these 5x5 blocks considered as potential target pixels. All other parameters were set at their default values.

For each of the possible radii, the accuracy of the connectivity models was assessed by using the testing dataset that was used for assessing the accuracy of the ENMs (see section 2.1.5). Firstly, the results of the habitat connectivity models were scaled from their original values to 0.0–1.0 because the range of the values differed between models. Secondly, the cumulative current between the presence and background points was compared using the Wilcox test – if the model represents connectivity, then presence points should have higher cumulative current than the background points (Jackson et al. 2016). Thirdly, the AUC of the models were calculated (Jackson et al. 2016) and compared – then the models with the highest AUC score were averaged. Then cumulative current between the presence and background points was compared and the AUC score was calculated.

Habitat connectivity was assessed using the Omniscape Julia package (Landau et al. 2021) in Julia (Bezanson et al. 2017) but the accuracy assessment was carried out using R (R Core Team 2023).

2.3 Results

The ecological niche models of each species achieved adequate accuracy with AUC values ranging from 0.8 to 0.9 (Table 2.2) and TSS values from 0.5 to 0.8 (Table 2.2). There were species-specific differences in habitat suitability (Figure 2.2–2.24). On average, habitat suitability was predicted to be highest along the southern part of Styria with low suitability towards the northwest (Figure 2.25 a,b). However, when summarised based on taxa, habitat suitability was predicted to be highest in the norther parts for amphibians (Figure 2.26 a,b) but highest in the southern parts for butterflies (Figure 2.29 a,b). For bats (Figure 2.27 a,b) and birds (Figure 2.28 a,b) it was high across most parts of the region.

Out of 264,620 pixels, 1,741 pixels (0.65%) did not contain suitable habitat for any of the 23 analysed species, while no pixels contained habitat for all 23 species (Figure 2.25 b). Most of the pixels (35,026, 13.2%) contained suitable habitat for only 10 species (Figure 2.25 b).

The habitat connectivity models of each species achieved AUC scores ranging from 0.3 to 0.9 (Table 2.2). Overall, the presence points had higher median connectivity than the background points for each species (Annex Figure A7.1–A7.23). The species *Bufotes viridis* and *Salamandra atra* had very low AUC scores (< 0.5) while the connectivity maps of *Tetrastes bonasia* had errors. The error here refers to high levels of connectivity predicted in the southern region of the study area even though this region did not contain any suitable habitat (Figure 2.24). Changing model parameters– radius and block size did not improve the model. This error did not occur in *Lyrurus tetrrix* (Figure 2.13) or *Tetrao urogallus* (Figure 2.23) species which had no suitable habitat in the southern region and negligible connectivity. Thus, the connectivity models of the three species were not included in the analysis of average habitat connectivity (Figure 2.25 c). There were also species-specific differences in habitat connectivity (Figure 2.2–2.24) and on average, it was predicted to be highest along the southern part of the region with low connectivity towards the northern regions (Figure 2.25 c).

Table 2.2 Accuracy of the ecological niche and connectivity models, along with the threshold determined to convert ecological niche models from probabilistic values to suitable/unsuitable categories.

Species	Ecological Niche Model		Habitat connectivity model	Threshold	No of pixels	
	AUC	TSS	AUC		Suitable	Unsuitable
<i>Bombina variegata</i>	0.91	0.65	0.50	0.50	149,513	114,667
<i>Bufo bufo</i>	0.87	0.57	0.77	0.50	196,440	67,740
<i>Bufotes viridis</i>	0.97	0.84	0.35	0.55	8,044	53,836
<i>Columba oenas</i>	0.87	0.53	0.83	0.55	109,915	154,267
<i>Dendrocopos syriacus</i>	0.93	0.72	0.92	0.55	2,029	262,591
<i>Dendrocoptes medius</i>	0.88	0.62	0.79	0.50	49,100	215,520
<i>Dryobates minor</i>	0.81	0.51	0.79	0.55	70,133	194,049
<i>Hyla arborea</i>	0.94	0.73	0.82	0.55	53,977	210,203
<i>Ichthyosaura alpestris</i>	0.88	0.65	0.63	0.50	130,447	133,733

<i>Lissotriton vulgaris</i>	0.88	0.65	0.82	0.55	130,026	134,154
<i>Lycaena dispar</i>	0.87	0.52	0.91	0.75	43,034	221,146
<i>Lyrurus tetrix</i>	0.92	0.74	0.95	0.55	102,235	161,947
<i>Melanargia galathea</i>	0.86	0.56	0.93	0.60	122,981	141,199
<i>Minois dryas</i>	0.90	0.64	0.90	0.50	123,849	140,331
<i>Parnassius mnemosyne</i>	0.90	0.66	0.82	0.70	86,647	177,533
<i>Picus canus</i>	0.84	0.52	0.81	0.50	132,306	131,876
<i>Rana dalmatina</i>	0.93	0.75	0.54	0.60	57,908	63,021
<i>Rana temporaria</i>	0.90	0.62	0.75	0.55	174,917	89,263
<i>Rhinolophus hipposideros</i>	0.88	0.56	0.90	0.55	160,126	104,494
<i>Salamandra atra</i>	0.89	0.68	0.42	0.65	113,001	86,787
<i>Salamandra salamandra</i>	0.94	0.73	0.82	0.50	135,144	129,036
<i>Tetrao urogallus</i>	0.93	0.68	0.93	0.75	101,027	163,593
<i>Tetrastes bonasia</i>	0.87	0.68	0.90	0.50	138,020	126,600

Figure 2.2 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.98) where values ≥ 0.50 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.71) models for *Bombina variegata*.

Figure 2.3 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.01–0.93) where values ≥ 0.50 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.35) models for *Bufo bufo*.

Figure 2.4 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.96) where values ≥ 0.55 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.50) models for *Bufotes viridis*.

Figure 2.5 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.02–0.91) where values ≥ 0.55 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.43) models for *Columba oenas*.

Figure 2.6 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.80) where values ≥ 0.55 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.38) models for *Dendrocopos syriacus*.

Figure 2.7 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.01–0.98) where values ≥ 0.50 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.66) models for *Dendrocytes medius*.

Figure 2.8 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.99) where values ≥ 0.55 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.62) models for *Dendrocytes minor*.

Figure 2.9 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.99) where values ≥ 0.55 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.23) models for *Hyla arborea*.

Figure 2.10 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.96) where values ≥ 0.50 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.32) models for *Ichthyosaura alpestris*.

Figure 2.11 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.01–0.93) where values ≥ 0.55 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.19) models for *Lissotriton vulgaris*.

Figure 2.12 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.96) where values ≥ 0.75 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.75) models for *Lycaena dispar*.

Figure 2.13 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.97) where values ≥ 0.55 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.38) models for *Lyrurus tetrix*.

Figure 2.14 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.97) where values ≥ 0.60 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.28) models for *Melanargia galathea*.

Figure 2.15 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.99) where values ≥ 0.50 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.81) models for *Minois dryas*.

Figure 2.16 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.99) where values ≥ 0.70 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.29) models for *Parnassius mnemosyne*.

Figure 2.17 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.04–0.91) where values ≥ 0.50 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.27) models for *Picus canus*.

Figure 2.18 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.04–0.98) where values ≥ 0.60 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.74) models for *Rana dalmatina*.

Figure 2.19 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.04–0.96) where values ≥ 0.55 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.36) models for *Rana temporaria*.

Figure 2.20 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.01–0.98) where values ≥ 0.55 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.46) models for *Rhinolophus hipposideros*.

Figure 2.21 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.98) where values ≥ 0.65 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.01–0.68) models for *Salamandra atra*.

Figure 2.22 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.00–0.96) where values ≥ 0.50 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.26) models for *Salamandra Salamandra*.

Figure 2.23 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.01–0.96) where values ≥ 0.75 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.38) models for *Tetrao urogallus*.

Figure 2.24 The (a) habitat suitability (range: 0.02–0.96) where values ≥ 0.50 are (b) suitable (1) habitat else unsuitable (0), and (c) habitat connectivity (range: 0.00–0.30) models for *Tetrastes bonasia*.

Figure 2.25 The (a) average habitat suitability, (b) summed suitable habitat, and (c) average habitat connectivity for all 23 species analysed (but 20 species for average habitat connectivity).

Figure 2.26 The (a) average habitat suitability, (b) summed suitable habitat, and (c) average habitat connectivity for all 10 amphibian species analysed (but 8 species for average habitat connectivity).

Figure 2.27 The (a) average habitat suitability, (b) summed suitable habitat, and (c) average habitat connectivity for the one bat species analysed.

Figure 2.28 The (a) average habitat suitability, (b) summed suitable habitat, and (c) average habitat connectivity for 8 bird species analysed (but 7 species for average habitat connectivity).

Figure 2.29 The (a) average habitat suitability, (b) summed suitable habitat, and (c) average habitat connectivity for 4 butterfly species analysed.

2.2.1 Outputs

The results described in Figure 2.25 b and Figure 2.25 c are accessible on the UU's Yoda platform. The files and metadata are accessible under: Research / research-wimby-data / wimby_results / D1.8_Impact assessment on terrestrial and marine fauna (b)_Styria. The uploaded results are described in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3 Description of the Styria results uploaded to YODA.

Results	Format
<p>Summed habitat suitability map: Habitat suitability of each species was modelled. The output from this is a habitat suitability map where the values range from 0.0 to 1.0 which represent lowest and highest suitability respectively. These probabilistic values were then transformed into binary values – 0 and 1 which represent unsuitable and suitable habitat using an optimal threshold. The threshold was selected using the sensitivity-specificity sum maximisation approach (Liu et al. 2005). The binary habitat suitability was then summed to result in the "summed_habitat suitability.tif" file. The value ranges from 0 to 18. Here, 0 indicates that the pixel does not contain suitable for any species while 18 indicates the pixel contains suitable habitat for 18 species. No pixel contains suitable habitat for all 23 species analysed.</p>	<p>The "summed_habitat suitability.tif" file is a raster in geotiff format with spatial resolution of 250 m and coordinate system of MGI / Austria Lambert (EPSG:31287)</p>
<p>Averaged habitat connectivity map: Habitat connectivity of each species was modelled. The output from this is a habitat connectivity map where the values range from 0.0 to N. Here, N varies from species to species. Thus, the results of were scaled from their original values to 0.0–1.0. The rescaled habitat connectivity maps were then averaged to result in the "average_habitat connectivity.tif" file. The value ranges from 0.0 to 0.22 which indicate lowest and highest connectivity. While habitat suitability was summed</p>	<p>The "average_habitat connectivity.tif" file is a raster in geotiff format with spatial resolution of 250 m and coordinate system of MGI / Austria Lambert (EPSG:31287).</p>

across the 23 species, for habitat connectivity the models of 20 species were averaged because the species *Bufo viridis* and *Salamandra atra* had very low AUC scores and *Tetrastes bonasia* had errors.

2.4 Discussion

Habitat suitability and connectivity of 23 species (10 amphibian, 1 bat, 8 bird, and 4 butterfly species) were analysed. The ecological niche models achieved accuracy with AUC and TSS scores greater than 0.8 and 0.5, respectively. The habitat connectivity models achieved AUC scores greater than 0.3 and the presence points on average had higher connectivity than the background points. There were species-specific differences in habitat suitability, with no overlap between all 23 species. Most of the pixels (13.2%) contained suitable habitat for 10 species. On average, habitat connectivity of the 23 species was highest in the southern part of the pilot region with low connectivity in the northern parts.

Species-specific differences in habitat suitability and connectivity maps reflect the specific habitat requirements of the analysed species. For example, the southern part of the study area had relatively low suitability and connectivity for *Lyrurus tetrix*, *Tetrastes bonasia* and *Tetrao urogallos*. This part of the study area had larger urban areas and less forest coverage which are unlikely to be occupied by the three grouse species, since these are forest birds (de Juana and Kirwan 2020a, b). In contrast, the southern parts of the pilot region Styria provide suitability habitat and connectivity for *Rhinolophus hipposideros* probably because this species can roost in buildings (Winter et al. 2020) and make use of different land cover in fragmented areas (Reiter et al. 2013).

As a pre-mitigation strategy to avoid or reduce negative effects of wind farms on terrestrial wildlife, existing guidelines recommend wind farm development to avoid areas contributing to the persistence of biodiversity (Bennun et al. 2021). In the context of this study, this would be the areas that contain overlapping suitable habitat for many species of high conservation value. It would be ecologically more appropriate to first consider wind farm development around areas that do not contain any suitable habitat followed by consideration of areas that are suitable for just one species.

Habitat connectivity promotes species dispersal and migration which is essential for gene flow between sub populations (Kunz et al. 2021). Loss of such areas can have cascading impacts on the population of the species (Kunz et al. 2021). The areas predicted to have the highest connectivity and patches that promote connectivity between isolated areas should not be considered as areas for wind farm construction. Instead, already fragmented land should be considered for wind farm construction (Diffendorfer et al. 2019; Kati et al. 2021), while sparsely (human) populated areas should be avoided (Helldin et al. 2012).

The study is limited by the number of species analysed. The multi-taxa habitat suitability and connectivity maps of the 23 species provided for the deliverable and the subsequent use in the WIMBY interactive map can help to raise awareness of the general public towards the habitats that are important for specific wildlife species; but the data do not cover the entire biodiversity in the region. Another limitation is the number of species presence points which can influence model accuracy (Wisniewski et al. 2008). The number of presence points also prevented the analysis of other bat species such as *Barbastella barbastellus* and *Eptesicus nilssonii* which had 62 and 72 presence points, respectively. Spatial bias is another issue with the presence points. Data cleaning and thinning was carried out to reduce the issue, but it cannot be completely corrected. The presence points were still clustered around certain areas, and this can affect model accuracy (Beck et al. 2014). The study is also limited by the lack of telemetry (e.g., Marques et al. 2020) and genetic (e.g., Kunz et al. 2021) data which would be the most appropriate type of data to assess the accuracy of the habitat connectivity models. However, due the lack of such data, presence points were instead used for accuracy assessment, similar to Koen et al. (2014). Model accuracy could also be increased by using additional predictors such as locations of caves for *Rhinolophus hipposideros* (Winter et al. 2020) or presence of species of the Ericaceae family such as *Vaccinium* spp. for *Tetrao urogallus* (Jacquin et al. 2005).

Effects of wind farms on wildlife, e.g., due to shadow flicker or noise (Coppes et al. 2020b), usually extend beyond the areas that are used for the erection of wind turbines themselves, but displacement distances of species are highly species-specific (Tolvanen et al. 2023) and might also depend on habitat structure (e.g., vegetation cover affects visibility of shadow flickering,

Nopp-Mayr et al. 2021). Spatially explicit, high-resolution information on the probability of occurrence of wildlife species and on landscape resistance patterns, which drive the dispersal of ground dwelling species, are usually neglected in regular planning processes of wind farms. Assessments of potential impacts are typically limited to a narrow area around planned wind farms without considering the regional or supra-regional aspects of available, species-specific habitats, of existing stepping stones and dispersal corridors. The latter are of major importance for the maintenance of gene flow, thereby preserving genetic diversity, and to minimise extinction risks, within meta-population systems (Kunz et al. 2021). The current models are provided for the region of Styria, Austria. However, a larger geographical scale should be considered when assessing impacts of potential wind farms on landscape connectivity (Guo et al. 2020).

A high proportion of the natural range of some species might fall within a restricted territory, while suitable habitats outside the territory might not exist. For these specific species of Community interest, listed in the Annex II of the Council Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (FFH, Council Directive 92/43/EEC 1992), the respective Member States have a particular responsibility. Austria has a particular responsibility for more than 700 species (fauna and flora) that occur only in Austria or slightly beyond its borders. These endemic and subendemic species are mainly occurring in areas at higher altitudes in Austria (Paar et al. 2023). Loss of such areas in Styria due to wind farm development or other types of infrastructures could impact not only the local, but also the global population of the species. Habitat connectivity also operates across large geographic scales. Areas of high connectivity along the boundaries of Styria could be connected to other areas of high connectivity of Austria or neighbouring countries. Thus, it is important to consider connectivity also along the boundaries to allow species to disperse or migrate and maintain gene flow among sub populations.

3. PILOT REGION: PANTELLERIA

3.1 Background

According to the European Climate Change Act, the total installed capacity of wind energy is expected to increase in the coming years to promote the transition to a carbon free energy production and to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. In particular, there is a growing interest in the great potential of offshore wind energy, as offshore wind farms (OWFs) might overcome the main limitations of onshore wind farms (land availability, habitat modification and social acceptance) (IPCC 2023). However, the expansion of OWFs has boosted the interest on the related impacts on the marine environment and biodiversity, since there is a lack of understanding of how OWFs and related infrastructure can be built, operated, and decommissioned, and how this could impact ecosystems and their functions (Papathanasopoulou et al. 2015; Raoux et al. 2017). The effects of OWFs are indeed many and varied and do not always result in negative impacts on marine fauna. There are several potential pathways through which OWFs can have positive impacts for marine fauna. First, the underwater structures of offshore wind turbines may provide new habitats for benthic marine species and attract fish and other marine organisms, supporting new communities (Raoux et al. 2017; Werner et al. 2024). Accordingly, wind farm structures, such as turbine foundations and cables, can act as artificial reefs, providing substrate for colonization by marine organisms. Studies have shown increased biodiversity and abundance of fish, invertebrates, and algae around wind farm structures compared to adjacent areas (Wilhelmsson et al. 2006). Second, the presence of wind farms can create “protected areas” where fishing and other activities are restricted, leading to reduced disturbance to marine fauna and enhanced habitat quality. These areas may serve as refuges for sensitive species, contributing to their conservation (Hammar et al. 2015). Third, by limiting access to fishing grounds, wind farms may indirectly benefit marine fauna by reducing fishing pressure and associated impacts such as habitat destruction and bycatch (Hammar et al. 2015).

On the other hand, OWFs may negatively influence marine fauna as the construction and operation phases can generate underwater noise, vibrations and electromagnetic fields affecting feeding, migration and reproductive behaviours of marine mammals, fish, and invertebrates

(Thomsen et al. 2006; Watson et al. 2024). Moreover, habitat modification due to the construction of OWFs can affect migratory patterns and movements along the water column of mammals and reptiles, such as large cetaceans that are attracted by the abundance of prey around the foundations but are then unable to avoid collision with the structures (Revolution Wind LLC 2020). Finally, the presence of OWFs can alter local hydrodynamics and sediment transport patterns, leading to changes in benthic habitats and species composition and affecting benthic fauna and associated food webs (Bergström et al. 2014; Dannheim et al. 2020).

Therefore, environmental impact assessments and careful planning are crucial to understanding and mitigating the potential negative effects of OWFs on marine species in specific locations. Regulations and guidelines are continually evolving to address these concerns and promote sustainable offshore wind energy development.

Ecological Niche Models (ENMs) help to identify the key environmental factors that influence the distribution of a species and are widely used in conservation biology for various purposes, such as biodiversity conservation (Melo-Merino et al. 2020). ENMs can predict the suitable habitat for a particular species based on environmental variables such as temperature, salinity, depth, and substrate type. This information helps conservationists to identify critical habitats for protection and restoration efforts (Guisan et al. 2013).

By overlaying ENM predictions with maps of human activities (e.g., fishing, shipping lanes, pollution), conservationists can identify areas where human pressure overlaps with important habitats. This allows for targeted conservation actions to mitigate these impacts and protect vulnerable species. The integration of ENMs into the spatial planning of OWFs can offer several benefits, indeed, ENMs can identify areas of high ecological importance and sensitivity, helping to avoid or minimize impacts on key habitats and species during the siting of OWFs. Therefore, ENMs provide a scientific basis for incorporating ecological considerations into spatial planning processes, facilitating transparent and evidence-based decision-making that balances environmental protection with renewable energy development goals.

Overall, ENMs play a crucial role in marine species conservation by providing valuable insights into species distributions, habitat preferences, and the potential impacts of human activities. The integration of ENMs into the spatial planning of OWFs enhances the sustainability and effectiveness of marine renewable energy development by minimizing environmental impacts and promoting the conservation of marine biodiversity.

In this report we describe the outcome of ENMs carried out to identify areas suitable for species listed in Descriptor 1 (Marine Biodiversity) of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC), a European Union Directive aimed at achieving and maintaining the good environmental status (GES). The primary objective of Descriptor 1 is to ensure that biodiversity is conserved, with a particular focus on conserving marine ecosystems, habitats, and species. The aim of this study was to assess whether areas around the Island of Pantelleria, relevant for the installation of OWFs, were suitable for species of interest, which may experience negative impacts from the wind farm infrastructures. In the second version of the deliverable, additional algorithms were used to attempt to improve the predictive performance of the ensemble model. In addition, a distinction was made between marine species that may experience negative impacts from the wind farm and marine species that may experience positive impacts from the wind farm. Two maps were produced to differentiate between areas of vulnerability and areas of potential benefit. Therefore, this study provides a useful tool to support the siting of OWFs in order to minimise the impact on marine fauna and consequently increase the social awareness and acceptance of citizens in the pilot site of the island of Pantelleria.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Study area

The study was carried out in Pantelleria, a small volcanic island 110 km off the coast of Sicily (Italy) with high potential for renewable energy production (Figure 3.1). The island's own electricity grid is mainly powered by diesel generators, but due to its location in one of the windiest areas in Italy, offshore wind energy could be a sustainable alternative.

Figure 3.1 Geographical location of Pantelleria Island.

3.2.2 Target species selection

Target species were selected based on the list of Descriptor 1 (Marine Biodiversity) of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC) for the assessment of good environmental status. Species were included in the study when occurrence data were available for the study area. Species occurrence data were downloaded from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) database [GBIF, 2024. Global Biodiversity Information Facility. World Wide Web electronic publication <http://www.gbif.org/>].

At the end, the following species were selected: ten fishes (the Osteichthyes *Coris julis*, *Diplodus sargus*, *Diplodus vulgaris*, *Epinephelus marginatus*, *Sarpa salpa* and *Spicara maena* and the Chondrichthyes *Leucoraja melitensis*, *Mustelus punctulatus*, *Raja clavata* and *Torpedo marmorata*), one reptile (*Caretta caretta*), and two mammals (*Stenella coeruleoalba* and *Tursiops truncatus*).

C. julis is a reef-associated demersal species, usually found at depth between 1 and 60 m. *D. sargus* is a marine and brackish demersal fish inhabiting coastal rocky reef areas and *Posidonia oceanica* beds at depth between 0 and 50 m, while *D. vulgaris* is a benthopelagic species that lives mainly on rocky bottoms, commonly at less than 50 m depth. *S. salpa* is a marine and brackish benthopelagic fish found at depth up to 70 m over

rocky bottoms and sandy areas with seagrasses and macroalgae. *E. marginatus* is a reef-associated fish, capable of reaching depths up to 300 m but mostly found within 50 m, which prefers to live in close contact with the seabed to find protection among rocks. *S. maena* is a pelagic-neritic species found in *P. oceanica* beds and on sandy, muddy and rocky bottoms between 30 and 130 m.

M. punctulatus is a demersal bottom-dwelling shark usually found at depth between 3 and 200 m. *L. melitensis* is a bathydemersal species, typical of deep waters (60–800 m), endemic of the coast of Tunisia and Malta and recorded also in Italy. *R. clavata* is a demersal fish that inhabits muddy, sandy and gravel bottoms from 10 to 300 m, but most common within 60 m. Adults undertake migrations moving from deeper offshore waters in autumn and winter to shallower waters in spring. *T. marmorata* is a marine and brackish fish typical of rocky reefs, seagrass beds and surrounding soft bottoms (2–370 m deep). This species lives in close contact with the seabed where it buries itself during the day to hide from predators. Both *R. clavata* and *T. marmorata* are characterized by electric organs that produce electric shocks to stun and immobilise prey. The loggerhead sea turtle *C. caretta* is widely distributed in the Mediterranean Sea and is particularly abundant in the southern Ionian Sea and the Sicilian Channel where several nesting sites are known. Like other sea turtles, this species is capable of large migrations between feeding and nesting areas depending on the life cycle period. Finally, *T. truncatus* and *S. coreuleoalba* are both dolphins that inhabit temperate and tropical waters, the former mainly in coastal areas and the latter in offshore waters. Both species are gregarious and, like other mammals, are capable of extensive movements and produce acoustic emissions, such as whistles and clicks, used to communicate with other individuals, locate prey and orient themselves while navigating.

Coastal species (*C. julis*, *D. sargus*, *D. vulgaris*, *E. marginatus*, *S. salpa*, and *S. maena*) typical of shallow waters are not expected to have suitable environmental conditions in the area around the Island of Pantelleria appropriate for the installation of OFWs (depth >200 m). However, we decided to keep them in the model for validation purposes.

3.2.3 Marine environmental data

Nine environmental variables were considered: concentration of nitrates (Data-Interpolating Variational Analysis DIVA interpolation, micromol/L), chlorophyll-a (mean at mean depth, mg/m³), phosphates (DIVA interpolation, micromol/L), silicates (DIVA interpolation, micromol/L), dissolved oxygen (DIVA interpolation, ml/l) and pH (DIVA interpolation) were obtained from Bio-ORACLE v.2.1 (Tyberghein et al. 2012). Bathymetry (meters), sea surface salinity (annual mean, Practical Salinity Scale-PSS) and sea surface temperature (annual mean, °C) data were obtained from MARSPEC (Sbrocco and Barber 2013). The raster files for each variable were converted to a WGS84 coordinate system with a spatial resolution of ~9.2 km using R (R Core Team 2023).

3.2.4 Ecological niche modeling

In the first version of the deliverable (D1.7) ENMs were estimated using four different algorithms; in particular Generalized Linear Model (GLM), Random Forest (RF), Max Entropy (MaxEnt) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithms were implemented. This second version of the deliverable has been enriched with additional algorithms, including Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS) and the Generalised Additive Model (GAM).

The species dataset was presence-only, and 1000 background points were randomly sampled throughout the study area. The presence data were randomly split into 30% and 70% for model testing and calibration respectively to avoid underestimating the model's accuracy (Araujo et al. 2005) and a 5-fold cross-validation procedure was used to estimate predictive performance of the models. Then, models were evaluated using the true skill statistic (TSS; Allouche et al. 2006) and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC; Fielding and Bell 1997). TSS values ranged from -1 to +1, with -1 corresponding to systematically wrong predictions and +1 to systematically correct predictions; a value of TSS > 0.6 indicates good performance. AUC scores ranged from 0 to 1, with 0 for systematically wrong model predictions and 1 for systematically perfect model predictions. AUC values > 0.6 indicate good performance.

Habitat suitability was mapped using the ensemble method combining the predictions of multiple individual base models to achieve more accurate and reliable predictions. Data were analysed using the sdm R package

(Naimi and Araújo 2016). Once the habitat suitability maps for each species had been obtained, the raster files were imported in QGIS (QGIS Development Team 2024). From each map the probabilities of occurrence were extracted using a point reticules and a composite indicator was created (see section 3.1.5 for more detail).

3.2.5 Sensitivity map

Composite indicators serve as a way to consolidate multiple measures or scores into a single value, providing a holistic view of a situation or phenomenon. The Additive Value Model (AVM) is a method for creating such reliable composite indicators (Cilluffo et al. 2024) and it involves several steps. First, one needs to identify the dimensions or attributes that will be included in the composite indicator. These dimensions can vary depending on the context, but they can include aspects like environmental characteristics (such as trace elements, good environmental status variables) or predicted values from models. Once the dimensions are identified, relative weights are assigned to each of them to reflect their importance in the overall assessment. These weights are crucial, as they determine how much each dimension contributes to the final composite indicator. Next, the dimensions are evaluated individually using appropriate metrics or data sources. After evaluating each dimension, the next step is to multiply the evaluated values by their respective weights and sum up these products. This calculation yields the composite indicator value, which provides a comprehensive assessment based on the chosen dimensions. Finally, the obtained composite indicator can be interpreted and communicated effectively. It serves as a concise representation of the overall situation, making it easier for policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders to understand and act upon the findings. In summary, composite indicators offer a powerful tool for synthesizing complex information and providing actionable insights for decision-making.

The additive value model is a linear method used to evaluate and quantify the joint effects or values of multiple factors or attributes. To ensure comparability among different factors and their corresponding weights, the standardized data values must be summed up, as shown in the following equation:

$$v(x) = \sum_{j=1}^k w_j v_j(x)$$

where $v_j(x)$ and w_j are the standardized value and the corresponding weight, respectively, for the j th attribute, where $j = 1, \dots, k$, and k representing the total number of the factors. The weights are such that $\sum_{j=1}^k w_j = 1$.

We used the habitat suitability values of each species as attributes to create the sensitivity map. In this case, a scoring algorithm generates scores for each attribute on a scale from 0.00 to 1.00. Standardized values are then calculated for each attribute:

$$v_j(x) = \frac{1 - e^{\frac{-(x_{high}-x)}{\rho}}}{1 - e^{\frac{-(x_{high}-x_{low})}{\rho}}}, j = 1, \dots, k$$

where $\rho = -\hat{r}(x_{high} - x_{low})$ and \hat{r} is the root of the function $f(r) = -0.5 + \frac{1 - e^{-z}}{1 - e^{-1}}$

in which $z = \frac{(x_{high}-x_{mid})}{(x_{high}-x_{low})}$. Then, each standardized attribute should be assigned a weight to evaluate its individual contribution to the composite score. We assigned weights based on the occurrence of each species, i.e. more frequently observed was that species higher was the weight. The final sensitivity indicator can assume values between 0 and 1, where one indicates higher sensitivity zones and zero indicates low sensitivity zones.

After obtaining the composite indicator, the Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) interpolation was used to estimate values at unmeasured locations with the aim of creating the sensitivity map. IDW interpolation is a spatial interpolation technique commonly used in geographic information systems (GIS) and geostatistics to estimate values at unmeasured locations based on known values at nearby locations. The IDW interpolation method assumes that the interpolating surface should be influenced primarily by nearby scatter points, with decreasing influence attributed to more distant points. The interpolating surface is generated by calculating a weighted average of point data. The weight assigned to each scatter point decreases proportionally with the distance from the interpolation point.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Marine environmental data

The marine environmental data used in ENMs are shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Values of marine environmental variables in the study area around Pantelleria: nitrates (micromol/L), chlorophyll-a (mean at mean depth; mg/m³), phosphates (micromol/L), silicates (micromol/L), dissolved oxygen (ml/l), and pH were obtained from Bio-ORACLE v.2.1, while bathymetry (meters), sea surface salinity (Practical Salinity Scale-PSS) and sea surface temperature (°C) were obtained from MARSPEC.

3.3.2 Ecological Niche Models

Osteichthyes

Coris julis

Figure 3.3 reports the predictive performance of each model for *Coris julis*, they were very good in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line).

Figure 3.3 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *C. julis*.

Table 3.1 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. All models reported excellent performance both in terms of AUC and of TSS.

Table 3.1 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *C. julis*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.81	0.70
RF	0.97	0.94
MaxEnt	0.92	0.85
SVM	0.86	0.79

Wide areas of offshore waters around Pantelleria Island resulted unsuitable for *Coris julis* (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4 Habitat suitability map for *Coris julis*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Diplodus sargus

Figure 3.5 reports the predictive performance of each model for *Diplodus sargus*; they were very good in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line).

Figure 3.5 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *D. sargus*.

Table 3.2 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. All models reported good performance both in terms of AUC and of TSS except for GLM.

Table 3.2 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *D. sargus*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.76	0.55
RF	0.86	0.83
MaxEnt	0.84	0.83
SVM	0.89	0.89

Wide areas of offshore waters around Pantelleria Island resulted unsuitable for *Diplodus sargus* (Figure 3.6).

Diplodus sargus

Figure 3.6 Habitat suitability map for *Diplodus sargus*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Diplodus vulgaris

Figure 3.7 reports the predictive performance of each model for *Diplodus vulgaris*; they were very good in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line).

Figure 3.7 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *D. vulgaris*.

Table 3.3 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. All models reported an excellent performance both in terms of AUC and of TSS.

Table 3.3 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *D. vulgaris*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.88	0.80
RF	0.99	0.97
MaxEnt	0.95	0.89
SVM	0.91	0.84

Wide areas of offshore waters around Pantelleria Island resulted unsuitable for *Diplodus vulgaris* (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8 Habitat suitability map for *Diplodus vulgaris*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Epinephelus marginatus

Figure 3.9 reports the predictive performance of each model for *Epinephelus marginatus*; they were good in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line).

Figure 3.9 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *E. marginatus*.

Table 3.4 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. All models reported a good performance both in terms of AUC and of TSS.

Table 3.4 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *E. marginatus*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.74	0.64
RF	0.94	0.87
MaxEnt	0.77	0.64
SVM	0.85	0.79

High suitability areas for *Epinephelus marginatus* were found on the east of Pantelleria, with small patches on the northwest (Figure 3.10).

Epinephelus marginatus

Figure 3.10 Habitat suitability map for *Epinephelus marginatus*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Sarpa salpa

Predictive performance of each model for *Sarpa salpa* are reported in Figure 3.11, they were very good in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line).

Figure 3.11 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *S. salpa*.

Table 3.5 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. All models reported from good to excellent performance both in terms of AUC and of TSS.

Table 3.5 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *S. salpa*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.74	0.60
RF	0.94	0.89
MaxEnt	0.92	0.87
SVM	0.85	0.76

Wide areas of offshore waters around Pantelleria Island resulted unsuitable for *Sarpa salpa* (Figure 3.12).

Figure 3.12 Habitat suitability map for *Sarpa salpa*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Spicara maena

Figure 3.13 reports the predictive performance of each model for *Spicara maena*; they were very good in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line).

Figure 3.13 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *S. maena*.

Table 3.6 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. All models reported a very good performance both in terms of AUC and of TSS.

Table 3.6 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *S. maena*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.86	0.77
RF	0.94	0.94
MaxEnt	0.85	0.84
SVM	0.96	0.96

Wide areas of offshore waters around Pantelleria Island resulted unsuitable for *Spicara maena* (Figure 3.14).

Figure 3.14 Habitat suitability map for *Spicara maena*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Chondroichthyes

Leucoraja melitensis

Figure 3.15 reports the predictive performance of each model for *Leucoraja melitensis*; they were good in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line). Unfortunately, it was not possible to estimate the SVM model, probably due to the imbalance between presence and absence data.

Figure 3.15 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *L. melitensis*.

Table 3.7 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. All models reported a good performance both in terms of AUC and of TSS.

Table 3.7 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *L. melitensis*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.90	0.89
RF	0.78	0.78
MaxEnt	0.80	0.62
SVM	-	-

High suitability areas for *Leucoraja melitensis* were found on the northwest of Pantelleria (Figure 3.16).

Figure 3.16 Habitat suitability map for *Leucoraja melitensis*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Mustelus punctulatus

All models, except for GLM, reported a very high predictive performance for *Mustelus punctulatus*, in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line) (Figure 3.17). Unfortunately, it was not possible to estimate the SVM model, probably due to the imbalance between presence and absence data.

Figure 3.17 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *M. punctulatus*.

Table 3.8 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. Only GLM reported an unsatisfactory performance.

Table 3.8 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *M. punctulatus*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.67	0.44
RF	0.92	0.92
MaxEnt	0.96	0.96
SVM	-	-

High suitability areas for *Mustelus punctulatus* were found on the north – northwest of Pantelleria (Figure 3.18).

Mustelus punctulatus

Figure 3.18 Habitat suitability map for *Mustelus punctulatus*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Raja clavate

All models, except for SVM, reported a good predictive performance for *Raja clavata*, in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line) (Figure 3.19).

Figure 3.19 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *R. clavate*.

Table 3.9 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. Only SVM reported an unsatisfactory performance.

Table 3.9 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *R. clavata*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.78	0.66
RF	0.93	0.93
MaxEnt	0.90	0.90
SVM	0.42	0.41

High suitability areas for *Raja clavata* were found on the north of Pantelleria (Figure 3.20).

Figure 3.20 Habitat suitability map for *Raja clavata*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Torpedo marmorata

All models showed a good predictive performance for *Torpedo marmorata*, in terms of discrimination power both in training set (red line) and in test set (blue line) (Figure 3.21).

Figure 3.21 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *T. marmorata*.

Table 3.10 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. Only SVM reported an unsatisfactory performance.

Table 3.10 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *T. marmorata*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.90	0.83
RF	0.84	0.84
MaxEnt	0.93	0.93
SVM	0.85	0.84

High suitability areas for *Torpedo marmorata* were found on the north of Pantelleria (Figure 3.22).

Torpedo marmorata

Figure 3.22 Habitat suitability map for *Torpedo marmorata*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Reptiles

Caretta caretta

All ENMs performed better than the random models for *Caretta caretta*. Figure 3.23 reports the predictive performance of each model for *Caretta caretta*; they were excellent in terms of discrimination power both in training (red line) and in test set (blue line).

Figure 3.23 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *C. caretta*.

Table 3.11 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. GLM reported the lower performance, even though it was above the acceptable thresholds.

Table 3.11 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *C. caretta*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.84	0.60
RF	0.88	0.70
MaxEnt	0.89	0.72
SVM	0.87	0.68

The habitat suitability for *Caretta caretta* showed suitability in the southwest of Pantelleria Island (Figure 3.24).

Figure 3.24 Habitat suitability map for *Caretta caretta*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Mammals

Stenella coeruleoalba

Figure 3.25 reports the predictive performance of each model for *Stenella coeruleoalba*; they were very good in terms of discrimination power in training set (red line) and a bit less in test set (blue line), even if a large variability was observed.

Figure 3.25 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *S. coeruleoalba*.

Table 3.12 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. All models reported a good performance both for AUC and TSS.

Table 3.12 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *S. coeruleoalba*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.83	0.72
RF	0.84	0.76
MaxEnt	0.89	0.85
SVM	0.82	0.74

The habitat suitability for *Stenella coeruleoalba* showed suitability in the north of Pantelleria (Figure 3.26).

Figure 3.26 Habitat suitability map for *Stenella coeruleoalba*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

Tursiops truncatus

Figure 3.27 reports the predictive performance of each model for *Tursiops truncatus*; they were very good in terms of discrimination power in training set (red line) and a bit less in test set (blue line), even if a large variability was observed.

Figure 3.27 Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve with AUC statistic computed in training (red line) and in test set (blue line) for *T. truncatus*.

Table 3.13 shows the AUC and TSS values for each model. In terms of AUC all models reported an acceptable performance, whereas, in terms of TSS only RF achieved the acceptable threshold of 0.60.

Table 3.13 Models AUC and TSS performance scores for *T. truncatus*.

Model	AUC	TSS
GLM	0.71	0.56
RF	0.79	0.65
MaxEnt	0.72	0.55
SVM	0.69	0.58

The habitat suitability for *Tursiops truncatus* showed suitability in the northeastern of Pantelleria, with a few other locations in the west (Figure 3.28).

Tursiops truncatus

Figure 3.28 Habitat suitability map for *Tursiops truncatus*. Colours from blue to yellow indicate a habitat suitability from 0 (unsuitable habitat) to 1 (high suitability habitat).

3.3.3 Variable importance

Table 3.14 shows the variable importance for each considered species. Overall bathymetry was the most important predictor for fish, with the marked exception of *Epinephelus marginatus*, which was influenced mainly by salinity. Looking at Chondroichthyes, habitat suitability of the rays was more affected by nutrients (phosphates) and dissolved oxygen. Habitat suitability for *Mustelus punctulatus* and *T. marmorata* was most influenced by bathymetry along with nutrients.

Nutrients and dissolved oxygen resulted the most important predictors for *Caretta caretta* and dolphins with pH also playing a role for the former.

Table 3.14 Variable importance (DO: dissolved oxygen; SSS: sea surface salinity; SST: sea surface temperature).

Species	Variables								
	Nitrates	Chlorophyll-a	Phosphates	Silicates	DO	pH	SSS	bathymetry	SST
<i>Osteichthyes</i>									
<i>Coris julis</i>	27.4	10.2	28.7	21.6	27.6	11.2	29.4	41.2	25.6
<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	33.9	24.5	24.2	16.9	28.3	13.4	23.5	43.5	8.3
<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	77	3.6	24.1	10.6	14	39.8	13.4	36.8	7.8
<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>	15.7	5	30.7	29.3	41.5	13.2	56.8	15.4	27.6
<i>Sarpa salpa</i>	21.8	24	20.5	18.4	31.7	6	5	34.3	9.2
<i>Spicara maena</i>	98.4	11.7	50.4	19.8	47.1	85.4	17.2	57	42.2
<i>Chondroichthyes</i>									
<i>Leucoraja melitensis</i>	16.2	1.9	34.5	16.8	52.3	8.1	15.4	7.7	14.8
<i>Mustelus punctulatus</i>	20.9	6.3	19.8	8.6	18.5	11.2	7	31.4	10.7
<i>Raja clavata</i>	29.4	23.2	46.3	21.9	54.8	18.1	28.8	3.8	42.9
<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	41.5	5.8	77.4	20.4	73	34.8	23.9	66.8	20.3
<i>Reptiles</i>									
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53.2	0.9	24.4	64.4	51.4	47.8	15.7	1.7	9.4
<i>Mammals</i>									
<i>Stenella coeruleoalba</i>	25.5	2.1	88.1	25.4	50.6	14.3	36.1	2.1	16.3
<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	25.3	5	53.8	36.4	39.8	22	6.9	21.9	3

3.3.4 Prediction capacity evaluation

The predictive ability of an ensemble model incorporating Generalized Linear Model (GLM), Random Forest (RF), Max Entropy (MaxEnt) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithms was compared with that of an ensemble model combining GLM, RF, MaxEnt, SVM, Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), multivariate adaptive regression splines (MARS) and Generalized Additive Model (GAM.). Area under the curve, sensitivity and specificity for each species were reported in Table 3.15. Since adding other algorithms does not imply a significant gain in prediction capacity for all species, ensemble prediction obtained using GLM, RF, MaxEnt and SVM was used as final model.

Table 3.15 Models AUC, sensitivity and specificity of ensemble prediction

	Four algorithms			All algorithms		
	AUC	sensitivit y	specificit y	AUC	sensitivit y	specificit y
<i>Osteichthyes</i>						
<i>Coris julis</i>	0.89 6	0.851	0.753	0.92 4	0.851	0.819
<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.91 2	0.870	0.780	0.91 9	0.886	0.829
<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	0.96 2	0.952	0.813	0.95 2	0.941	0.853
<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>	0.86 1	0.840	0.737	0.90 3	0.821	0.818
<i>Sarpa salpa</i>	0.91 1	0.859	0.744	0.92 5	0.878	0.821
<i>Spicara maena</i>	0.99 7	0.995	0.892	0.99 3	0.997	0.922
<i>Chondroichthyes</i>						
<i>Leucoraja melitensis</i>	0.99 6	0.994	0.886	0.99 5	0.993	0.917
<i>Mustelus punctulatus</i>	0.98 5	0.959	0.871	0.98 5	0.981	0.908
<i>Raja clavata</i>	0.97 5	0.986	0.859	0.97 9	0.987	0.908
<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	0.95 6	0.943	0.819	0.96 4	0.970	0.870

	<i>Reptiles</i>					
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	0.868	0.802	0.712	0.871	0.803	0.748
	<i>Mammals</i>					
<i>Stenella coeruleoalba</i>	0.933	0.888	0.775	0.939	0.883	0.829
<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	0.868	0.792	0.792	0.868	0.762	0.771

3.3.5 Sensitivity map

The composite indicator produced by all ensemble predictions is shown in Figure 3.29. The sensitivity map showed a potential sensitive area extending along the northwest-southeast axis in the southern part of Pantelleria Island.

Figure 3.29 Sensitivity map in the study area around Pantelleria. The sensitivity index ranges from 0 (low sensitivity areas, green) to 1 (high sensitivity areas, red).

3.3.6 Vulnerability and beneficial maps

As the wind farm structures provide a suitable habitat for some species by creating artificial reefs that provide protection and food (Werner et al. 2024, Hammar et al. 2015), two different maps have been produced.

The first one (Figure 3.30), namely a vulnerability map, includes all species (*Mustelus punctulatus*, *Leucoraja melitensis*, *Raja clavate*, *Torpedo marmorata*, *Caretta caretta*, *Stenella coeruleoalba* and *Tursiops truncatus*) that may be adversely affected by the construction and operation phases of a wind farm, which generate underwater noise, vibration and electromagnetic fields that affect the migration and reproductive behaviour of marine mammals and invertebrates (Thomsen et al. 2006; Watson et al. 2024).

Figure 3.30 Vulnerability map in the study area around Pantelleria. The index ranges from 0 (low presence of vulnerable species, green) to 1 (high presence of vulnerable species, red).

The second one (Figure 3.31), namely a beneficial map, includes all species (*Coris julis*, *Diplodus sargus*, *Diplodus vulgaris*, *Epinephelus marginatus*, *Sarpa salpa* and *Spicara maena*) that may experience a beneficial effect from the construction of a wind farm.

Figure 3.31 Beneficial map in the study area around Pantelleria. The index ranges from 0 (low presence of species that may have a beneficial effect, aquamarine color) to 1 (high presence of species that may have a beneficial effect, dark blue color).

3.3.7 Outputs

Habitat suitability maps for each species (13 maps) are accessible on the UU’s Yoda platform. The files and metadata are accessible under: Research / research-wimby-data / wimby_results / D1.8_Impact assessment on terrestrial and marine fauna (b)_Pantelleria. The results uploaded are described in Table 3.16.

Table 3.16 Description of the Pantelleria results uploaded to YODA.

Results	Format
Habitat suitability of each species was modelled. The output from this is a habitat	The "species_RASTER.tif" file is a raster in geotiff format with spatial resolution of 10

suitability map where the values range from 0.0 to 1.0 which represent lowest and highest suitability respectively.	km and coordinate system of WGS 84 (EPSG:4326).
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3.4 Discussion

Using ENMs, a characterization of the environmental niches of thirteen marine species and their potential distributional patterns in the basin around Pantelleria Island (Sicily, Italy) was provided. The inclusion of three additional machine learning models – Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS) and Generalised Additive Model (GAM) – to the four previously used models (Generalised Linear Model (GLM), Random Forest (RF), Max Entropy (MaxEnt) and Support Vector Machine (SVM)) did not improve the predictive performance of the ensemble model. In fact, beyond a certain point, adding more models to an ensemble only leads to marginal improvements in AUC, known as the performance plateau (Bonab and Can 2019). As the first four algorithms (GLM, RF, MaxEnt and SVM) gave satisfactory results, all subsequent evaluations were based on them.

From the models, habitat suitability was predicted and mapped for six bony fish (*Coris julis*, *Diplodus sargus*, *Diplodus vulgaris*, *Epinephelus marginatus*, *Sarpa salpa* and *Spicara maena*), one shark (*Mustelus punctulatus*), three rays (*Leucoraja melitensis*, *Raja clavata* and *Torpedo marmorata*), the loggerhead turtle (*Caretta caretta*) and two dolphins (*Stenella coeruleoalba* and *Tursiops truncatus*), for which occurrence data were available for the area of Pantelleria Island. Dissolved nutrients and bathymetry were overall important predictors for different species.

Variable importance varied among species, indicating the influence of different environmental factors on habitat suitability. Combining outputs of habitat suitability, a sensitivity map to assess potential areas of higher sensitivity, due to the presence of multiple species, was created. This sensitivity map can therefore help to support offshore wind farm (OWF) siting within the framework of sustainable development. Our sensitivity map highlighted a potential sensitive area extending along the northwest-southeast axis in the southern part of Pantelleria Island.

Findings showed that the area around Pantelleria was suitable for *L. melitensis* (ray), *M. punctulatus* (shark), *R. clavata*, *T. marmorata* (rays), *C. caretta* (turtle), *S. coeruleoalba* and *T. truncates*, (dolphins), species with a habitat suitability >0.30 . Most of the aforementioned species are included in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species [IUCN 2024. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2023-1. <<https://www.iucnredlist.org>> ISSN 2307-8235], therefore they are important to be considered in a potential impact assessment of OWFs.

The study area around the Island of Pantelleria was found unsuitable for the other examined species (*C. julis*, *D. sargus*, *D. vulgaris*, *E. marginatus*, *S. salpa*, and *S. maena*). As indicated in the methods section, these are in fact coastal species, commonly found in shallow waters and associated with rocky substrates or seagrass beds. Consequently, and as expected, they did not find favourable conditions in installation areas of OWFs and their inclusion in the study provided an internal validation of the models. While the area of potential interests for wind farm installation, due to its high depth, is not naturally colonised by species (*C. julis*, *D. sargus*, *D. vulgaris*, *E. marginatus*, *S. salpa*, and *S. maena*) typical of the coastal zone, the presence of wind farm may offer suitable substrates and habitats for such littoral species (Li et al. 2023; Reubens et al. 2014).

For species like *L. melitensis*, *R. clavata* and *T. marmorata*, OWF installations may disrupt preferred habitats or feeding grounds. In addition, *R. clavata* and *T. marmorata* may be particularly sensitive to noise disturbance due to their electro-receptive abilities, which they use for navigation and hunting (Abramic et al. 2022; Bat et al. 2013).

Regarding *M. punctulatus*, the construction and operation of OWFs can generate underwater noise, which may affect the activity of these sharks (Abramic et al. 2022). Similarly, the power cables associated with OWFs can generate electromagnetic fields that affect shark prey detection ability (Hermans et al. 2024; Westerberg and Lagenfelt 2008).

C. caretta can be affected by OWFs in a number of ways. Vessel movements associated with survey and installation activities at OWFs may inadvertently strike sea turtles such as loggerheads (Foley et al. 2019). These collisions can result in injury or death, in particular in areas of reduced visibility. During

turbine assembly and maintenance, the turbidity of the water increases due to the resuspension of sediment, increasing the risk of turtles colliding with the OWF structures but also with the boats used to carry out the work. Moreover, *C. caretta* migration can be disrupted by underwater noise from wind turbines and local magnetic disturbances (Irwin and Lohmann 2005; Nelms et al. 2016).

Similarly, the physical structures of OWFs, such as foundations and cables, can create obstacles for *T. truncatus* and *S. coeruleoalba*. This can lead to entanglement or collision risks. Dolphins may also alter their movement patterns to avoid these structures, which can have an impact on their feeding and migration routes. Moreover, submarine power cables associated with OWFs can emit electromagnetic fields, which can interfere with the sensory perception of dolphins used for navigation and communication (Riefolo et al. 2016). Finally, dolphins rely heavily on sounds for communication, navigation, and hunting. Increased noise levels from OWFs can disrupt their natural behaviour, communication, and even lead to displacement from important habitats (Bailey et al. 2010; Thomsen et al. 2006).

Some limitations of our work must be considered. First, the accuracy of ENM outputs depends on the quality and availability of input data. In marine environments, data on species distribution and environment features are often limited. Second, ENM typically focuses on abiotic environmental factors and may not fully capture the influence of biotic interactions, such as predation, competition, and symbiosis, on species distribution. Finally, ENM results can be sensitive to the spatial and temporal scale of analysis.

This study has also several strengths. ENMs can accurately predict the distribution of species based on environmental variables. By modelling the ecological niche of a species, we can forecast how changes in environmental conditions, such as those caused by human activities like OWFs, might affect species' distribution. ENM allows for the integration of various environmental data layers, such as temperature, salinity, pH, and other habitat characteristics. This comprehensive approach enables to consider multiple factors that influence species distribution and abundance. ENM provides spatially explicit results, allowing finding areas where environmental impacts on marine species are likely to be most

significant. This information is crucial for spatial planning and management of human activities in marine environments.

This work underlines the value of using ENMs for estimating habitat suitability maps. Combining results derived from ENM for each target species can help in the process of biodiversity conservation, supporting strategic environmental assessments and spatial planning. Furthermore, the sensitivity, vulnerability and potential beneficial maps created can be used to identify key marine areas for different species, with the aim of supporting OWF siting within the framework of sustainable development and for improving citizens' understanding of the complex processes involved in marine spatial planning, thus supporting social awareness and engagement.

4. PILOT REGION: ROGALAND

All information on the Met Centre offshore wind test station and description of its potential impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity including mitigation measures can be found in deliverable D1.7 (a) section 4 (pages 71–95).

5. CONCLUSIONS

While a rapid development of renewable energy sources and deployment of wind farms is necessary to reach climate goals, it faces significant challenges due to low acceptance amongst societal actors. Next to concerns about landscape scenicness, and about noise or health impacts, there are concerns about negative impacts of wind farms on ecosystems. Ecosystems and biodiversity are also threatened by climate change and its consequences. Taking people's concerns seriously by providing comprehensive information on various aspects is a first step in raising acceptance and increasing societal engagement, which is key for a broad deployment of wind energy across the European Union.

The effects of wind farms are usually assessed within environmental impact assessments for potential wind farm sites, and different studies have shown direct (e.g., collision) and indirect (e.g., habitat loss) impacts of wind farms on fauna. Ecological impacts of wind farms must be investigated at European, national and sub-national scales to consider ecological processes (e.g., migration, broad biogeographic patterns) that occur at broader scales. The studies performed in the pilot sites Styria (Austria), Pantelleria (Italy) and Rogaland (Norway) demonstrate a workflow for fine-scale assessments of potential effects of targeted wind power plants on wildlife. Thereby, consequences of losses of occurrence areas are shown in a spatial context. In addition, the full environmental impact assessment for the pilot region Rogaland (Norway) provides insights into potential impacts on the local marine environment (see D1.7 a).

The outputs provided for the three pilot regions can provide valuable information for societal actors and can be used to raise awareness towards the multiple land demands that exist. Land is already under strong pressure, as various claims on the land exist (e.g., settlements, food production (agriculture, fisheries), tourism, infrastructure). Available space for wildlife is highly influenced by humans and potential land for wildlife is limited (biodiversity - wind energy - land use nexus, Kati et al. 2021). Therefore, strategic spatial planning and appropriate siting of wind farms is important to minimize effects on ecosystems and wildlife. Habitat suitability, connectivity and sensitivity maps provided for the pilot sites Styria (Austria)

and Pantelleria (Italy), respectively, can be used to identify key areas for specific species of high concern (e.g., threatened species). However, detailed knowledge on species distribution and species habitat requirements are necessary to assess whether species might be affected by a potential wind farm. The results from the pilot site in Rogaland (Norway, see D1.7 (a)) details the potential impact of an OWF, after the siting has already been determined. Ecological niche models and sensitivity maps can be an important tool for future environmental impact assessments. In addition, adequate mitigation measures must be developed, because effects of wind farms on wildlife are highly species-specific. Collision risk can be reduced by painting turbine blades and towers, or by curtailment during periods of low wind speed. The use of deterrents can also reduce collision risks, however, it is accompanied by habitat loss if potential habitat for breeding or foraging is lost.

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7. ANNEX

Table A7.1 Predictors used for modelling habitat suitability.

Species	Predictors used (after removal of highly correlated predictors)
<i>Bombina variegata</i>	Tree cover density, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average temperature in the coldest month, land cover
<i>Bufo bufo</i>	Tree cover density, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, land cover
<i>Bufo viridis</i>	Tree cover density, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average daily maximum temperature, land cover
<i>Columba oenas</i>	Elevation (quadratic), tree height, land cover
<i>Dendrocopos syriacus</i>	Elevation (quadratic), tree height, average precipitation, land cover
<i>Dendrocoptes medius</i>	Tree height, percent of broadleaf forest, average precipitation, average daily maximum temperature
<i>Dryobates minor</i>	Elevation (quadratic), tree height, land cover
<i>Hyla arborea</i>	Tree cover density, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, land cover
<i>Ichthyosaura alpestris</i>	Tree cover density, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, land cover
<i>Lissotriton vulgaris</i>	Tree cover density, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, land cover
<i>Lycaena dispar</i>	Aspect, tree cover density, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, wind speed, land cover
<i>Lyrurus tetrix</i>	Elevation (quadratic), aspect, slope, tree canopy, distance to alpine grassland, distance to urban areas, land cover
<i>Melanargia galathea</i>	Aspect, tree cover density, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, wind speed, land cover
<i>Minois dryas</i>	Aspect, tree cover density, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, wind speed, land cover
<i>Parnassius mnemosyne</i>	Aspect, tree cover density, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, wind speed, land cover

<i>Picus canus</i>	Tree height, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, land cover
<i>Rana dalmatina</i>	Tree cover density, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, land cover
<i>Rana temporaria</i>	Tree cover density, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, land cover
<i>Rhinolophus hipposideros</i>	Tree height, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average daily temperature maximum, land cover
<i>Salamandra atra</i>	Elevation, tree cover density, average relative humidity, average precipitation, land cover
<i>Salamandra salamandra</i>	Tree cover density, distance to waterbody, average relative humidity, average precipitation, average minimum temperature in the coldest month, land cover
<i>Tetrao urogallus</i>	Elevation (quadratic), slope, aspect, tree height, distance to coniferous forest, distance to urban area and land cover.
<i>Tetrastes bonasia</i>	Elevation (quadratic), slope, aspect, tree height, distance to coniferous forest, land cover.

Figure A7.1 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Bombina variegata*.

Figure A7.2 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Bufo bufo*.

Figure A7.3 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Bufotes viridis*.

Figure A7.4 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Columba oenas*.

Figure A7.5 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Dendrocopos syriacus*.

Figure A7.6 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Dendrocoptes medius*.

Figure A7.7 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Dryobates minor*.

Figure A7.8 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Hyla arborea*.

Figure A7.9 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Ichthyosaura alpestris*.

Figure A7.10 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Lissotriton vulgaris*.

Figure A7.11 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Lycaena dispar*.

Figure A7.12 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Lyrurus tetrix*.

Figure A7.13 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Melanargia galathea*.

Figure A7.14 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Minois dryas*.

Figure A7.15 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Parnassius mnemosyne*.

Figure A7.16 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Picus canus*.

Figure A7.17 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Rana dalmatina*.

Figure A7.18 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Rana temporaria*.

Figure A7.19 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Rhinolophus hipposideros*.

Figure A7.20 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Salamandra atra*.

Figure A7.21 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Salamandra salamandra*.

Figure A7.22 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Tetrao urogallus*.

Figure A7.23 Boxplot and violin plots showing cumulative current/ habitat connectivity of the background and presence points for *Tetrastes bonasia*.